

Preprint Review in 4 steps

Reading preprints? Interested in being a peer reviewer? This brief guide will help you get started in 4 simple steps!

Through Preprint Peer Review, you can contribute to open science by:

- Providing early feedback to authors
- Adding important context and scrutiny to published research
- Making the review process transparent

Additionally, you can:

- Hone your analytical and writing skills
- Get credit for reviews and contributions to the scientific community.

Resources

Discover a range of useful resources here:

<https://bit.ly/asapbio-preprint-review-guide>

1 Picking the preprint

Whether you're picking a preprint to review as an individual or as part of a preprint review club, consider these questions when selecting the preprint:

Do you have the time and expertise to give valuable feedback? Note that you can focus your feedback on specific areas of the work.

Can you provide objective feedback without or despite a potential conflict of interest?

Is the preprint the most recent version or is a revised version available/published in a journal?

2 Reading the preprint

Browse the preprint to get an overview of the topic, experiments done and conclusions. Get a general idea of the length and any extra reading necessary.

Read the document critically, annotating important points, strengths, and weaknesses. This may involve one or several rounds of reading, depending on your experience and scope of the review. Use the checklist below to check off addressed questions as you go!

Main findings:

What is the hypothesis?

What are the main findings?

What are the gaps that still need to be filled?

What is the significance of the paper?

Revisions required:

Are the results robust?

Does the data sufficiently support the conclusions?

What additional work might be needed to strengthen the conclusions?

What are the flaws (if any) of the experimental and research design?

Transparency of reporting:

Are the methods robust and rigorous?

Are the statistical tests sufficient or is further analysis needed?

Is the available data sufficient to evaluate the manuscript?

Is the literature properly referenced?

3 Writing the review

What kind of review are you writing?

Reviews can be in different formats and based on what type of review you're writing, the specific steps may differ. The review can be in the form of compiled comments that you synthesized during reading. Alternatively, you can address specific questions based on the guidelines provided by the platform you're using or only a section of the article. Either way, these steps can help!

Drafting the review

While writing the report, bear in mind that the aim of the review is to help the authors improve their article. Highlight the strengths and positive aspects of the manuscript.

Be concise, clear and objective.

A review can be structured following these broad guidelines:

Summary

Include a brief overview of what the study is about, its context and conclusions. An effort should be made in highlighting the main points of strength and its significance as well as major flaws, if any.

Once the major flaws of the work have been identified, comment on how their severity impacts the article. When proposing revisions, clearly communicate what they are.

Major Issues

- A lack of strong evidence for conclusions
- A lack of adequate controls
- Poor presentation of the data

Minor Issues

- Errors in citations
- Ambiguous areas
- Mislabelled figures or tables etc. Mention where these errors can be found (eg, line number)

4 Sharing your review

Once your review is ready, it's time to share it. Though you can share it privately with the authors, posting it publicly will benefit other readers, help you network, and allow the authors to address commonly asked questions publicly.

Choosing where to publish your review

PREreview is our platform of choice, because it links to your ORCID, allows anonymity, provides a DOI, and appears on Society. Other options are available (see Resources box).

Importantly, if the preprint server of choice offers a commenting function, we recommend to post a comment linking to your review, to increase visibility.

To sign or not to sign?

If you opt to post your review publicly, you can remain anonymous. However, signing your review gives you more credit for your contribution and lays the foundations for new collaborations and connections. Regardless of which option you choose, your contribution is valuable!

Licensing your review

As copyright holders, you and any co-authors can decide how to give others permission to reuse your reviews. Generally, we encourage you to select an open license, such as CC-BY, to facilitate indexing by indexing services to archive the content of your review, and also its reuse.

If the preprint review service does not offer an opportunity to choose a license when posting, the following text can be added:

"This work is licensed under CC BY 4.0".

For more info on Creative Commons licenses, see Resources.

Use the ASAPbio FAST principles while writing!

Modified from: <https://asapbio.org/fast-principles-for-preprint-feedback>

FOCUS on the science

- The scientific, not the personal
- The science, not the journal
- The content of the preprint

Be APPROPRIATE

- Behave responsibly and with integrity
- Engage in scientific discourse
- Reflect on possibly biases
- Polish the tone

Give SPECIFIC feedback

- Assess if claims are supported by data
- Indicate if critical or optional
- Make it useful
- Be candid

Be TRANSPARENT

- Sign (or don't sign) your reviews
- Acknowledge oversights
- Credit contributors